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Chemical companies in OECD countries

Between 2005 and 2022 they grew on average by 15.27% in the countries considered

The OECD calculates the number of chemical companies in OECD countries. Data is available for the period between 2005 and 2022.

Chemical companies in OECD countries in 2022. In 2022, the chemicals and chemicals manufacturing sector in Europe showed significant variability between different countries, reflecting differences in market size, production capacity, and industrial tradition. Among the main European economies, France stands out with a total of 4,336 companies active in the sector, followed closely by Italy with 3,899 companies. Germany, famously one of the world's leaders in the chemical sector, registered 3,634 companies, highlighting a robust industrial presence, but smaller than France and Italy. Spain follows with 3,597 companies, demonstrating considerable activity in the sector. In Eastern Europe, Poland emerges as the main player with 3,045 companies, indicating growing capacity and development in the chemical sector. The Czech Republic, with 1,849 companies, and Romania, with 1,001 companies, also show a significant presence. The industrial presence in the Netherlands is represented by 1,272 companies, a considerable number that reflects the country's strategic position as a commercial and logistics hub in Europe. In Southern Europe, Greece has 982 companies and Portugal 918, suggesting moderate but stable chemical activity. Bulgaria and Belgium have 744 and 737 companies respectively, while Serbia and Hungary follow with 706 and 689 companies. These data indicate an active and diverse chemical industry across the region. In Scandinavia, Sweden leads with 674 companies, followed by Finland with 426 and Denmark with 280 companies. Norway, although with a smaller number, still has 258 active businesses, demonstrating a significant presence in a region known for its technological and industrial excellence. The presence of the chemical industry in small European countries is more limited. In Slovenia there are 264 companies, in Latvia 252, and in Lithuania 221. Other countries such as Estonia and North Macedonia have 146 and 114 companies respectively, while Cyprus and Malta show a minimal presence with 67 and 42 companies respectively. Luxembourg closes the list with just 17 companies, reflecting the country's small size. In Central Europe, Austria has 642 companies, a significant number demonstrating robust industrial activity. Switzerland, known for its excellence in the pharmaceutical sector, registers 446 companies in the chemical sector. Slovakia, with 581 companies, shows a solid industrial presence. Croatia and Costa Rica, with 400 and 340 companies respectively, highlight a growing chemical industry. Israel, despite being geographically outside of Europe, is included in the list with 451 companies, signaling a strong presence in the chemical sector. This reflects Israel's ability to innovate and develop advanced technologies, including in the chemical

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sector. Overall, these data show a diverse European landscape, with countries varying significantly in terms of the number of companies active in the chemical manufacturing sector. Major economies, such as France, Italy, Germany and Spain, dominate the sector in terms of the number of companies, while Eastern and Southern European countries show a significant, but generally smaller presence. Scandinavia and Central Europe also contribute significantly, demonstrating that the chemical industry is distributed across the entire European continent with considerable diversification and specialization at a national level.

Chemical companies in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022. The analysis of data relating to companies operating in the chemical manufacturing sector between 2005 and 2022 reveals an evolving industrial landscape with varied dynamics among the different European countries and beyond. The changes recorded show significant variations both in absolute and percentage terms, reflecting different economic, political and market trends. In Austria, the number of companies increased from 340 to 642, with a percentage change of 302.00% and an absolute change of 88.82. This substantial increase reflects significant growth in the Austrian chemical industry, likely supported by favorable policies and investments in innovation. France saw a significant increase, from 3,257 to 4,336 companies, with a percentage change of 1079.00% and an absolute change of 33.13. This increase can be attributed to the strength of the French chemical sector, supported by a strong industrial base and innovation capacity. Germany, historically a leader in the chemical sector, recorded an increase from 2,908 to 3,634 companies, with a percentage change of 726.00% and an absolute change of 24.97. This continued growth underlines the resilience and adaptability of the German chemical industry. Poland showed impressive growth, from 1,960 to 3,045 companies, with a percentage change of 1085.00% and an absolute change of 55.36. This significant increase reflects the country's economic development and the expansion of its industrial base. The Czech Republic saw an increase from 1,505 to 1,849 companies, with a percentage change of 344.00% and an absolute change of 22.86. This figure indicates solid growth in the Czech chemical sector, probably supported by investments and economic reforms. In the Netherlands, the number of companies increased from 612 to 1,272, with a percentage change of 660.00% and an absolute change of 107.84. This remarkable increase suggests a favorable environment for the chemical industry, thanks also to the country's strategic position as a commercial hub. Belgium recorded moderate growth, from 672 to 737 companies, with a percentage change of 65.00% and an absolute change of 9.67. This increase suggests stability in the sector, with slight expansion. In Bulgaria, the number of companies increased from 584 to 744, with a percentage change of 160.00% and an absolute change of 27.40. This increase indicates moderate growth in the chemical sector. Costa Rica saw an increase from 246 to 340 companies, with a percentage change of 94.00% and an absolute change of 38.21. This suggests an expansion of the chemical sector, probably supported by government incentives. In Latvia, companies increased from 113 to 252, with a percentage change of 139.00% and an absolute change of 123.01, while in Lithuania the number increased from 97 to 221, with a percentage change of 124.00% and an absolute change of 127.84. Both countries have seen substantial growth, reflecting the development of their chemical industries. Denmark recorded a modest increase, from 271 to 280 companies, with a percentage change of 9.00% and an absolute change of 3.32. This indicates stability in the Danish chemical sector with limited growth. In Hungary, the number of companies increased from 654 to 689, with a percentage change of 35.00% and an absolute change of 5.35, suggesting stable and moderate growth. Slovenia saw an increase from 160 to 264 companies, with a percentage change of 104.00% and an absolute change of 65.00. Slovakia, on the other hand, recorded an increase from 132 to 581 companies, with a percentage change of 449.00% and an absolute change of 340.15. This latest figure highlights a significant expansion of the Slovak chemical sector. Italy recorded a significant decline, from 5,031 to 3,899 companies, with a negative percentage change of -1132.00% and an absolute change of -22.50. This decline could be attributed to various factors, including

relocation, the economic crisis and international competition. Spain also saw a decrease, from 3,854 to 3,597 companies, with a percentage change of -257.00% and an absolute change of -6.67. This decline could reflect the country's economic difficulties in recent years. In Sweden, the number of companies decreased from 815 to 674, with a percentage change of -141.00% and an absolute change of -17.30, suggesting a contraction in the Swedish chemical sector. Romania saw a slight decrease, from 1,050 to 1,001 companies, with a percentage change of -49.00% and an absolute change of -4.67. This small drop could reflect a phase of stabilization or restructuring of the sector. Portugal recorded a slight decline from 921 to 918 companies, with a percentage change of -3.00% and an absolute change of -0.33, indicating substantial stability with a slight downturn. In summary, the analysis of data from 2005 to 2022 shows a complex and dynamic picture of the chemical sector in Europe and other regions. While some countries such as France, Germany and Poland have seen significant growth, others such as Italy, Spain and Sweden have recorded declines. These variations reflect a combination of economic factors, industrial policies, investments in innovation and the ability to adapt to global challenges.

Conclusions. The number of chemical companies in the OECD countries considered grew by an average of 15.27% between 2005 and 2022. The countries with the highest growth in the number of chemical companies between 2005 and 2022 were Slovakia (+340.15%), Lithuania (+127.84%) and Latvia (+123.01%). There were also countries where the number of chemical companies decreased, such as Spain (-6.67%), Sweden (-17.3%) and Italy (-22.5%). Italy is the country that has suffered the most significant loss of chemical companies in absolute terms, with a decrease of 3,899 units between 2005 and 2022. Expressed as a percentage of the number of chemical companies in 2022, 13.06% are located in France, 11.74% in Italy, 10.94% in Germany, 10.83% in Spain and 9.17% in Poland.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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